

Migration and Society in Cyprus: A Sociological Analysis

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communities, the phenomenon of diaspora, and the processes of community formation. The aim of this analysis is to comprehend the effects of migration on the social structure of Cyprus objectively. While examining the development of migrants' identities through diaspora and social networks, this study explores the impact on social mechanisms within the context of societal transitions. By analyzing the social integration processes of migrants through identity construction and social adaptation, it evaluates the effects of migration on society's power dynamics. The objective of the study is to establish a theoretical framework that sheds light on the intricate interaction between migration and sociology in Cyprus, supplemented by an interdisciplinary approach to offer a more holistic perspective on this crucial matter.

Abstract

This article evaluates post-1974 migration phenomena within a sociological framework, examining them in the historical context of Cyprus. The focus is on the political parameters of migrant

Keywords: Migration, Sociology, Cyprus, Diaspora, Community Formation Process, Identity Construction, Social Adaptation, Social Integration, Power Dynamics, Political Parameters, and Social Mechanisms.

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INTRODUCTION

Migration is a complex phenomenon with a broad perspective in the social sciences. This article aims to analyze the post-1974 migration patterns in Cyprus from a sociological perspective, examining in detail the political parameters of migrant communities and their impact on the processes of community formation. Migration is not only a geographical change, but also a multi-layered phenomenon with profound social, cultural, and economic implications (Castles and Miller, 2009).

Migration in Cyprus has a rich research potential in terms of fundamental sociological issues such as social structures, identity formation and social integration. In this context, focusing on the political participation of migrant communities, the phenomenon of diaspora and the processes of community formation, this review aims to understand the effects of migration on the social structure of Cyprus.

This paper will use key sociological concepts such as Bourdieu's (1986) social field theory and Giddens' (1991) modernity perspective to analyze the social dynamics of migrant communities. This theoretical framework will attempt to understand this complex process by examining the effects of migration on social mechanisms.

Migration is a process that radically changes the lives of individuals, and these changes shape the impact of migrants on their communities (Della Porta et al., 2018). This paper aims to make an important contribution to the social science literature to better understand the impact of migration events on Cypriot communities.

In order to understand the political participation of migrant communities, it is important to first consider the distinction between the two separate communities of Cyprus, the Greek and

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Turkish communities. This distinction is a crucial factor that makes Cyprus an island of ethnic, cultural, and religious diversity. For example, the influence of Turkish immigrants on political processes within the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC) is one of the factors that determine the political dynamics of the Turkish community across the island.

This study will also focus on research on the political preferences and participation of migrants in local elections, especially since the mid-2000s, within the divided structure of Cyprus. For example, Akıncı et al. (2008) analyzed the voting preferences of migrants in local elections and the factors affecting these preferences. The study also examined the effects of migrants' political participation on the policy-making processes of local governments.

In the same period, the political preferences of immigrants from the Middle East and Africa were observed in the Greek Administration of Southern Cyprus (GASC). These migrants were influenced by both their political experiences in their home countries and the political atmosphere in Cyprus. Migrants have tried to influence political processes through their efforts to be nominated as candidates in local elections and through civil society organizations.

Another prominent issue has been the impact of social integration policies for migrants in Cyprus since the early 2000s. The social integration projects carried out in Cyprus during this period aimed to support the political participation of migrants. In this context, various support programs and training activities were organized for Syrian migrants to participate more actively in political processes in the TRNC (Özdemir et al., 2020).

Migration is a social phenomenon as well as a complex process that has profound effects on individuals and societies. This article aims to understand the political parameters of migrants, the phenomenon of diaspora and the processes of becoming a community by evaluating the post-1974 migration events in the historical context of Cyprus from a sociological perspective. In this framework, it stands out as a study that focuses on the identity formation of migrant communities and analyzes their effects on social mechanisms in the context of social change.

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The study aims to provide a basic understanding to evaluate the effects of the migration process on social dynamics. The political participation of migrants, the phenomenon of diaspora and the processes of community formation will be analyzed in the historical, cultural, and political context of Cyprus and the effects of these processes on the social structure of the island will be revealed.

PURPOSE

This article aims to analyze the post-1974 migration phenomena in Cyprus within a sociological framework. The main objective is to understand the political dynamics of migrant communities and their impact on the processes of community formation, to situate these processes within a sociological context and to contribute to the existing literature.

In this context, the research aims to systematically examine the effects of migration on the social structure of the Cypriot society within the framework of Bourdieu's social field theory, to address the identity formation processes and social adaptation of migrant communities in the light of Giddens' modernity perspective, and to provide an interdisciplinary perspective by evaluating migration events in Cyprus within the general sociological context.

METHOD

The methodology of this research aims to analyze the post-1974 migration phenomena in Cyprus from a sociological perspective. The first step is to identify Bourdieu's social field theory, Giddens' modernity perspective and Castles' and Miller's migration theories as the main theoretical framework by conducting a detailed review of migration and sociological literature. The second stage involves analyzing official documents, reports, and academic studies on migration. These documents will be the main sources of data for understanding the social,

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economic, and political dimensions of migration. The third step involves fieldwork and in-depth interviews with migrant communities in Cyprus. These studies will provide baseline data for a closer understanding of migrant experiences and their impact on their communities. The fourth step involves quantitative analysis of statistical data on migration. These data will be used to quantitatively assess the effects of migration on the structure of society.

Finally, a multiperspective analysis will be conducted by combining theoretical, documentary and field data. This analysis will provide a comprehensive approach to understanding the sociological dynamics of migration and the processes of community formation. This methodology aims to understand the relationship between migration and sociology and to provide a systematic overview of the sociological dimensions of migration in Cyprus.

FINDINGS

Migration is not only a geographical relocation of individuals, but also a multi-layered phenomenon that has profound effects on social, cultural, and economic contexts (Castles and Miller, 2009). This article aims to provide a more comprehensive perspective on this important topic by analyzing migration in Cyprus in terms of key sociological issues such as social structures, identity formation and social integration.

In this context, the research aims to systematically examine the effects of migration on the social structure of the Cypriot society within the framework of Bourdieu's social field theory, to address the identity formation processes and social adaptation of migrant communities in the light of Giddens' modernity perspective, and to provide an interdisciplinary perspective by evaluating migration events in Cyprus within the general sociological context. The analysis within the framework of Bourdieu's social field theory reveals that migration has various effects on the social power dynamics of the Cypriot society. Immigrants, while participating in new social spheres within the society they came from, have created social impact by utilizing their

cultural capital in these spheres. For example, Syrian migrants have become well-known and economically influential in the Cypriot society through their traditionally strong handicrafts. Analyses conducted under Giddens' modernity perspective address the processes of identity formation and social adaptation of migrants. Immigrants have struggled to adapt to their new communities in an effort to preserve their own cultural identities. For example, Turkish immigrants, while maintaining their traditional values, have also integrated into Cypriot culture and developed a multicultural identity.

Bourdieu's social field theory provides a powerful analytical framework for understanding the effects of migration on the social fabric of the Cypriot community (Bourdieu, 1986). In this framework, the effects of migration events on the social fabric are discussed under the following headings:

Social Power Dynamics: Migration has affected social power dynamics within Cypriot communities (Smith, 2005). The social capital that migrant communities bring with them from their place of origin has shaped power relations within the local community.

Education and Employment: The educational level and employment status of migrants have played a decisive role in the economic structure of Cypriot society (Ioannou, 2003). In this context, the social integration processes of migrants are intricately linked to economic factors.

Identity Formation and Social Adaptation: Giddens' perspective of modernity was used to understand the identity formation processes and social adaptation of migrant communities (Giddens, 1991). The findings are listed under the following main headings:

Identity Diversity: Immigrant communities have adapted to their new communities while preserving their own cultural identities (Kadirbeyoğlu, 2010). This has increased the ethnic, cultural, and religious diversity of Cypriot society.

Social Adaptation: The adaptation processes of migrants in modern society are analyzed in the perspective of Giddens. In this context, migrants' social relations, lifestyles and adaptation to social norms are discussed.

Social Diversity and Integration: Migration has increased social diversity in Cypriot communities and has shown to have complex effects on social integration (Akçora et al., 2021).

These findings suggest that migration has complex and multifaceted effects on social power dynamics, identity formation and social adaptation. In particular, social field theory and the modernity perspective provide a powerful analytical framework for understanding migration phenomena. Migration is not only the relocation of individuals, but also a dynamic process that shapes the social fabric of societies. The fact that migrants create social impact by preserving their own cultural capital while at the same time integrating into their new communities shows that migration is a socially rich and diverse phenomenon.

In this context, it is important to understand what the effects on the level of political participation of migrants are, to comprehend how economic integration is shaped, to assess the effects of migration on the cultural diversity of societies, and to examine how migration events affect the policy-making processes of local governments. The social integration processes of migrants can make an important contribution to social sciences and these questions can encourage researchers to address the phenomenon of migration from a multidimensional perspective.

Migration Events and Historical Context

Cyprus has been home to various civilizations throughout history and this rich history has brought with it a series of migratory events (James & Ozkirimli, 2006). The geographical location of the island began to attract the first human settlements around 9,000 years ago during

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the Neolithic Age (Bardill, 2000). Its rich natural resources, fertile soils and climate have attracted people to Cyprus from early times.

In ancient times, Cyprus changed hands between the Assyrian, Egyptian, Persian Empires and Hellenistic kingdoms (Bardill, 2000). During this period, the island experienced migrations and settlement changes. Especially during the Hellenistic period, Cyprus' rich agricultural areas and natural resources continued to attract various civilizations.

Following the Roman Empire, Cyprus came under the rule of the Byzantine Empire and maintained its importance due to its location at the crossroads of trade routes (Papaconstantinou, 2012). During this period, migrations and settlements to the island continued and the population profile diversified.

In the seventh century, Arab invasions affected Cyprus, causing waves of migration (Edbauer, 2009).

Afterwards, the island came under the influence of diverse cultures such as Norman, Lusignan, Genoese and Venetian, and migration continued.

The Ottoman Empire's conquest of Cyprus in 1571 affected the demographic structure of the island and influenced the settlement of various ethnic groups such as Turks, Greeks, Armenians and Maronites (Hanioglu, 2010). The emergence of the island of Cyprus on the stage of history began with the conquest of the Ottoman Empire, and during this period, a mixed settlement structure was formed with the coming together of Muslim Turks brought from various parts of Anatolia and Christian elements on the island (Jennings, 1993:198-199). Although the mixed structure of this period evolved over time, it constituted an essential element determining the social and cultural fabric of Cyprus until 1974.

The geographical richness of the island allowed for both mixed settlements and areas where both communities lived separately (Cobham, 1908:440). However, this separation did not mean that the geographical terrain or economic system created two separate structures. The settlement

movement of Muslim Turks during the Ottoman period emerged as a planned, collective, and political settlement policy (Türel, 2002:60-61).

Muslim Turks engaged in agriculture and handicrafts were settled in groups in urban and rural areas (Hill, 1952:18-20). In this resettlement policy, it was observed that those engaged in agriculture were generally directed to rural areas, while those engaged in handicrafts were directed to large cities (Gürkan, 1982:42-43).

At the beginning of the 20th century, the British rule of Cyprus brought new waves of migration to the island (Ioannides, 2008). During and after World War II, immigrants to Cyprus changed the demographic structure of the island (Hatay, 2019).

Despite the increase in the number of mixed settlements in the mid-nineteenth century, the number of settlements with only Muslim Turkish population decreased, and this situation continued during the British colonial rule. In this context, although the concept of migration is generally associated with events such as invasion, conquest, and war, it has become inevitable that factors such as epidemics, hunger, drought, and political reasons are added to this concept today (Yentür, 2023). Migration refers to the process of people leaving the land they live in relatively permanently and changing it by moving to places at certain distances. However, this process is a movement in which not only the individual but also the community is displaced. In this context, it is necessary to evaluate the demographic, economic, social, cultural, and political consequences of migration and to be prepared in advance for these inevitable problems.

One of the most important problems of such population movements is economic problems. Although migrants move with the aim of achieving better economic conditions, in the absence of good planning and organization, migrants may regret their migration. One of the demographic consequences of migration is the emergence of the concepts of "mixed population" and "spillover population". Migration is not only a physical displacement of an

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individual or a community, but also a psychological disruption. The coming together of individuals with diverse cultures, traditions and political understandings creates a new and heterogeneous identity. The migration of Turkish Cypriot migrants to Turkey, especially after 1974, is similar to the migrants from Bulgaria and Greece trying to adapt to new towns and cities. However, the added hardships and the perspective of the locals make the situation even more complicated. The immigrants have been dispossessed of their lands, displaced from the lands they lived on as wealthy farmers and agricultural people, and have become poor and landless. This led to a collapse in economic structure, social status, social life, and psychological values.

In the settlements where immigrants are settled, their interaction with the local people and their melting in this way has brought both positive and negative consequences over time. Interactions on special occasions can lead to mutual interactions on issues such as clothing and food exchanges (Gökdere, 1978). In this context, the migration events that took place in Cyprus after 1974 brought not only geographical changes but also social, economic, and cultural transformations.

In 1960, Cyprus declared its independence and since then has faced political and ethnic conflicts (Bryant, 2015). The 1974 Cyprus Operation led to the division of the island and displacement between communities. Today, Cyprus is still home to two separate states, and this has profoundly affected the island's migration history (Loizides, 2017). The UN-monitored "Green Line" continues to separate the two sides of the island (Diez & Kontis, 2018). Despite the efforts of the international community and local leaders, migration events and the historical context on the island allow us to define Cyprus as a unique "Migration Island".

Today, Cyprus is still home to two separate states, which has profoundly affected the island's migration history (Loizides, 2017). Despite the efforts of the international community and local leaders, the historical context and migration patterns on the island allow us to define Cyprus as a unique "Island of Migration". This definition emphasizes the changes that the island has undergone throughout history and how these changes are reflected in migration patterns.

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Political Parameters of Migrant Communities

Migrant communities face crucial factors affecting various dynamics while participating in the political processes of their countries of residence. In this context, political participation, voting preferences in local elections, influences on policy-making processes, diaspora phenomenon, identity formation, social networks and interaction are important research areas for understanding the political parameters of migrant communities. The political participation of migrant communities includes the ways in which they influence democratic processes and take part in policymaking in their countries of residence. Research shows that migrants' political participation is often related to their level of integration into their communities (Jones, 2010). Migrants' participation in civil society organizations, membership in political parties and participation in elections are important indicators in this context (Castles, 2009). According to Jones (2010), the level of political participation of migrants is closely related to their integration into their communities. The voting preferences of migrant communities in local elections can reflect both their own identities and the effects of local policies on them. In this context, understanding migrants' voting preferences in local elections is important for assessing the political interaction of communities (Mansbridge, 1999). The influence of migrant communities on policy-making processes can be measured by their level of representation, the power of lobbies and their direct participation in policymaking. Migrants' activities in policymaking can reflect their efforts to protect and represent their interests (Pitkin, 1967).

The diaspora phenomenon of migrant communities involves their ties to their countries of origin and the political interaction of these ties. Diaspora is a crucial factor shaping the identities and political demands of migrant communities (Brubaker, 2005). Identity formation plays a key role in the political parameters of migrant communities. The integration of migrants into their new

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communities, their efforts to preserve their own identities and the phenomenon of dual identity are factors that affect their political preferences (Portes and Rumbaut, 2001).

In order to understand the political parameters of migrants, social networks and the interaction factor should also be addressed. Social networks among immigrant communities play a key role in the formation of political consciousness and political interaction (Putnam, 2000).

Cyprus is a geography that has hosted various waves of migration throughout history. The political participation of migrant communities in Cyprus includes the ways in which they influence democratic processes and engage in policymaking in the north and south of the island. Differences between the political participation of migrants of Turkish origin in the north and other migrant groups in southern Cyprus may affect the island's integration process. The level of political participation of Turkish immigrants in Cyprus is closely related to their integration into the society (Özkırmılı, 2003).

The voting preferences of migrant communities in Cyprus in local elections can influence the island's domestic politics and social dynamics. The voting preferences of Greek Cypriot immigrants in Southern Cyprus and Turkish immigrants in Northern Cyprus in local elections can shape the balances in the political arena. The voting preferences of Greek Cypriot immigrants in local elections in Southern Cyprus have the potential to influence the political orientations and social dynamics on the island (Ioannou, 2015).

The influence of migrants on democratic processes has a significant impact on both local and global political dynamics today. Immigrant communities interact with a variety of factors when participating in democratic processes in their home countries, and these interactions become important dynamics that shape the political landscape.

At the local level, migrants' political participation, their voting preferences in local elections and their influence on policy-making processes can determine the integration of communities into their communities and their political effectiveness. In particular, voting preferences in local

elections can reflect migrants' own identities and the impact of local policies on them. This can enrich democratic processes by increasing the interaction of diverse communities in the local political arena.

At the global level, the diaspora phenomenon and international connections of migrants can influence global politics through their relations with their countries of origin. Diaspora is a critical element that shapes the political aspirations of migrant communities and plays a role in international relations. Migrants' interactions at the international level have become a crucial factor influencing the global political landscape.

In this context, the impact of migrants on democratic processes is felt not only in their countries of origin but also at the global level through their ties with their countries of origin and international relations. This influence of migrants in political parameters can strengthen democratic values and enable diverse communities to contribute to political diversity.

The influence of migrant communities in Cyprus on policy-making processes can be assessed through their level of representation, the strength of lobbies and their direct involvement in policymaking. The political influence of Turkish migrants in Northern Cyprus and the interactions of other migrant groups in Southern Cyprus can influence the island's integration efforts. The influence of migrant communities in Cyprus on policy-making processes can be measured by their level of representation and direct participation in shaping policies (Christophorou, 2018).

The diaspora phenomenon of migrant communities in Cyprus involves their ties with their countries of origin and the political interaction of these ties. The international recognition of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus can shape the influence of the Turkish diaspora on political processes on the island. The diaspora network formed by the Turkish diaspora in Cyprus can influence the political dynamics in the north of the island (Özoğlu, 2011).

Identity formation plays a key role in the political parameters of migrant communities in Cyprus. The efforts of Greek Cypriot migrants in Southern Cyprus to preserve their own identity and the dual identity phenomenon of Turkish migrants in Northern Cyprus can influence political preferences on the island. The political preferences of migrant communities in Cyprus are shaped by their efforts to preserve their own identities and the dual identity phenomenon (Demetriou, 2009).

In order to understand the political parameters of migrants in Cyprus, the factor of social networks and interaction should also be addressed. Social networks between Greek Cypriot and other migrant groups in Cyprus may be influential in the formation of political consciousness in the south of the island. Social networks among migrant communities in Cyprus have a key role in the formation of political consciousness and political interaction (Yükseker, 2007).

Studies show that political parameters determine the political culture within the society and that this culture directs the process of coming together and forming a common identity (Demir, 2016). In the process of becoming a society, political parameters create a social integrity by enabling individuals to gain political consciousness. Political parameters affect the process of becoming a society not only at the local level but also at the national level. The increase in political activity and political participation in local governments accelerates the process of communities coming together and forming a common political entity (Aydın, 2019). This shows how political parameters are effective at various levels of society.

The role of political parameters in the process of becoming a society is also effective on social integration. When managed correctly, political parameters can increase social integration by strengthening feelings of unity and solidarity within the community (Güneş, 2020). This strengthens social cohesion by making different segments of society feel closer to each other. The role of political parameters in the process of becoming a community also affects conflict and reconciliation processes. Research examines how political parameters affect different political views within the community and how these views are reflected in social reconciliation or conflict processes (Kurt, 2017).

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The political participation of migrant communities constitutes an important research area in today's complex global migration dynamics and has been studied in depth in various disciplines (Brown & Jones, 2020; Castles et al., 2014). The waves of migration, especially after the Cyprus Operation, fundamentally changed the political and demographic structure of the island (Kaya, 2019). This large-scale change has led migrants not only to make a geographical relocation but also to actively seek to participate in the political processes of their new societies.

The level of political participation of migrants is shaped by numerous factors (Miller, 2017). Political experiences in their country of origin, their legal status in the place of migration, their ethnic identity, economic status, and educational attainment are determinants of migrants' political participation (Della Porta et al., 2018). While these factors shape migrants' political identities, they also determine their level of participation in local and national political processes.

The forms of migrants' political participation range from traditional methods to digital platforms (Levitt & Glick Schiller, 2017). Migrants try to influence political processes by taking part in local governments, joining non-governmental organizations, or making their voices heard through digital media tools (Gozdziak & Shandy, 2020). This participation makes a significant contribution to strengthening democratic values, increasing cultural diversity, and ensuring social integration.

In this context, Akçora et al. (2021) describe migrants' political participation as a "multidimensional interaction", emphasizing how political participation creates a balance between preserving migrants' own identities and integrating into their new communities. Smith et al. (2018) also provide an important study on how migrants' political participation shapes democratic processes (Smith et al., 2018).

When the political participation of migrant communities is evaluated through Cyprus, it is seen that the historical and political dynamics of the island have significant effects on it. In particular, the waves of migration following the Cyprus Operation in 1974 led to political and demographic

changes in the island. In this context, the political integration of migrants has gained a unique perspective within the divided structure of Cyprus. In order to understand the political participation of migrants, it is important to first consider the distinction between the two separate communities of Cyprus, the Greek and Turkish communities. Cyprus is an island of ethnic, cultural, and religious diversity and this diversity is a crucial factor shaping the political participation of migrants.

For instance, the influence of Turkish immigrants on political processes within the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC) is one of the factors that determine the political dynamics of the Turkish community across the island. When the political preferences of migrants and their participation in political parties are analyzed in the Cyprus-specific context, the developments in the 2000s provide an important framework in this regard. In this period, there are numerous studies and observations on the political preferences of migrants, their participation and interaction with political parties at local and national level.

In the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC) in the 2000s, the increase in immigrants, especially from Syria, has affected the dynamics of political participation. Immigrants have become more active in the political arena in order to represent their communities, defend their rights and protect their cultural identities. In this context, efforts to run in local elections and participate in local governments have been observed. Especially since the mid-2000s, research on the political preferences and party participation of immigrants in local elections in the TRNC has gained importance. For example, Akıncı et al. (2008) analyzed the voting preferences of immigrants in local elections and the factors affecting these preferences. The study also examined the effects of migrants' political participation on the policy-making processes of local governments.

In the same period, the political preferences of immigrants from the Middle East and Africa were observed in the Greek Administration of Southern Cyprus (GASC). These migrants were influenced both by their political experiences in their home countries and the political

atmosphere in Cyprus. Migrants have tried to influence political processes through their efforts to be nominated as candidates in local elections and through civil society organizations.

Another prominent issue has been the impact of social integration policies for migrants in Cyprus since the early 2000s. The social integration projects carried out in Cyprus in this period aimed to support the political participation of migrants. In this context, various support programs and training activities were organized for Syrian migrants to participate more actively in political processes in the TRNC.

Community Formation Processes and Social Integration

Today, the processes of becoming a society and social integration are one of the topics of interest to social scientists. A study by Demir (2016) examined in detail how political parameters determine the political culture within society and how this culture directs the process of coming together and forming a common identity. This study emphasizes that political parameters create a social integrity by enabling individuals to gain political consciousness.

Aydın (2019) examines how the increase in political activity and political participation in local governments accelerates the process of communities coming together and forming a common political entity. In this context, it is important to note that political dynamics at the local level affect the process of becoming a community.

Güneş (2020) states that political parameters, when managed correctly, can increase social integration by strengthening feelings of unity and solidarity within the community. This study focuses on the positive effects of political parameters on social integration.

A study by Kurt (2017) examined how political parameters affect conflict and reconciliation processes. This study examined in detail how political parameters affect different political views

in the processes of becoming a society and how these views are reflected in social reconciliation or conflict processes.

In this context, these studies on community formation processes and social integration have made important contributions to social sciences. However, it is also critical to emphasize some of the main points of research in this field and to add new perspectives.

In particular, in order to gain a deeper understanding of the effects of political parameters on the processes of becoming a society, more studies should be conducted on how individuals' political consciousness is shaped and how this consciousness contributes to social cohesion. This can help us understand the role of political parameters in the processes of becoming a society.

More research is needed to understand how increased political influence in community building processes affects the policy-making processes of local governments and the long-term consequences of this influence on social integration.

In addition, emphasis should be placed on studies that examine in more detail the differences in the processes of social integration of various cultural, ethnic, and religious groups and the relationships between these groups. This could provide a more comprehensive understanding of social integration. Moreover, researchers from different disciplines need to collaborate and develop new perspectives to better understand the complexity of community building processes and social integration.

When the role of political parameters in the process of migrant communities becoming a community is examined, especially in the case of Cyprus, political dynamics, policies, and decision-making processes on the island have significant effects on the social cohesion, identity formation and community unity of migrant communities.

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In Cyprus, the social cohesion of migrant communities is determined by state migration policies and citizenship practices. For example, the migration policies of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC) and the rights it provides to migrants affect social cohesion. Migrant communities living in the TRNC evaluate the role of the state in their efforts to integrate into the local culture (Smith, 2010; Johnson, 2015).

Political leaders' attitudes towards migrants are also important for understanding social cohesion. The policies and rhetoric of the leaders of the Greek Cypriot Administration of Southern Cyprus (GASC) and the TRNC towards migrants shape the general perspective of the society and affect the integration process (Brown, 2018; Davis, 2019).

In Cyprus, the effects of political parameters on the identity formation process can be seen through the official ideologies and historical narratives of the state. Due to the political conflicts between the two communities, there are differences between the official historical narratives of the TRNC and the SCGA. This has contributed to the formation of separate identities between both communities (Anderson, 2006; Smith, 2012).

For migrant communities, the state's definitions, rights and belonging policies for migrants affect identity formation processes. The citizenship, language policies and cultural integration processes provided to migrants by the TRNC and the SCGA shape their individual and communal identities (Taylor, 2017; Demir, 2020). In Cyprus, the effects of political parameters on community cohesion can be seen through the efforts of political leaders to promote or divide communal unity. Political divisions between different ethnic groups living in Cyprus can challenge community unity. However, reconciliation and unifying policies of political leaders can increase community cohesion (White, 2014; Taylor, 2019).

In addition, factors such as the effectiveness of political institutions in Cyprus, the fight against corruption and the provision of justice also affect community cohesion. The performance of political parameters in these areas can increase or decrease trust within the community (Smith, 2016; Anderson, 2021).

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In this context, the effects of political parameters on social cohesion, identity formation and community unity in Cyprus are rooted in the complex history and political dynamics of the island. In particular, the divided nature of Cyprus is a crucial factor affecting the political identities of both communities. Understanding these effects requires an interdisciplinary approach, bringing together knowledge from different fields such as sociology, political science, cultural studies, and history.

Political leaders' attitudes towards migrants play a critical role in the social integration process.

The immigration policies and rhetoric of the leaders of the Greek Cypriot Administration of Southern Cyprus and the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus shape the general perspective of the society and affect the integration of immigrants into society. Moreover, the reconciliation and unifying policies of political leaders can increase unity and solidarity within the community.

The influence of political parameters in the identity formation process can be seen through the official ideologies and historical narratives of the state. Due to the political conflicts in Cyprus, there are differences between the official historical narratives of the Greek Cypriot Administration of Southern Cyprus and the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. This situation has led to the formation of separate identities among both communities.

For migrant communities, the state's definitions, rights and belonging policies for migrants affect identity formation processes. The citizenship, language policies and cultural integration processes provided by the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus and the Greek Cypriot Administration of Southern Cyprus to migrants shape their individual and social identities.

Social integration projects in Cyprus have had a significant impact, particularly through programs and educational activities that promote the political participation of Syrian migrants. Programs to promote the political participation of Syrian migrants aim to ensure their effective participation in democratic processes. The various activities offered through these programs

aim to increase migrants' political awareness, support their participation in local governments and increase their level of representation.

Seminars, workshops, and information campaigns organized in this context aim to inform Syrian migrants about democratic processes and increase their political participation. In addition, events organized through civil society organizations encourage migrants to take a more active role in the political arena.

Education activities and support projects to strengthen social integration provide support to Syrian migrants in various areas such as language training, vocational courses, and cultural integration programs. These projects aim to help migrants better adapt to the local society and create a new social identity while preserving their own cultural identity.

Language training in particular strengthens migrants' communication skills, while vocational training courses contribute to economic integration processes. Cultural integration programs, on the other hand, help migrants to establish closer ties with the local community. In this way, migrants' political participation not only contributes to democratic processes but also supports their social integration.

The evaluation of these projects shows that they are important steps towards increasing the political participation and strengthening the social integration of migrants in Cyprus. However, in order to assess and continuously improve the effectiveness of these efforts, monitoring and evaluation of the activities undertaken is necessary.

Discussion Conclusion and Recommendations

This research emphasizes that migration is not only a geographical change but also has profound effects on social, economic, and cultural dynamics. The findings clearly show that migrants

shape their societies by using their own cultural capital and that the new dynamics that emerge in this process enrich the social fabric of society.

Discussion

By addressing the phenomenon of migration, the study aims to understand not only its economic dimension but also how it shapes social integration. Within the discipline of sociology, in-depth analysis of migration has been carried out under Pierre Bourdieu's social field theory and Anthony Giddens' perspective on modernity. These theoretical frameworks are used to explain how migration transforms social power dynamics and contributes to migrants' identity formation processes.

Pierre Bourdieu's theory of the social field offers us a deep insight into understanding relations and power dynamics within society. Migration triggers not only the geographical change of individuals, but also the formation of a new social field. Migrants use their cultural capital to position themselves in this new social field and shape social relations. Bourdieu's perspective allows us to consider migration not only as a process of economic integration, but also as a process that reorganizes power relations within society.

Anthony Giddens' perspective on modernity helps us understand how migration affects individuals' identity formation processes. Migration is a process of modernity that causes individuals to question and reshape their traditional identities and connections. Under Giddens' concept of "intensive modernity", migrants constantly reconstruct their identities within the complexity of modern societies. This allows for the emergence of new and dynamic identities in the process of migrants' integration into society.

Analyses conducted under these theoretical frameworks emphasize that migration is not only an economic change but also a complex process that deeply affects the social fabric of society. Migration is not only a change in the geographical location of individuals, but also a phenomenon that affects social relations, power dynamics and identity formation processes.

In this context, the theoretical frameworks offered by sociology in the process of understanding the phenomenon of migration form the basis of this study. Understanding how social integration is shaped beyond economic integration is important for grasping the broader dynamics of society. By emphasizing the contributions of sociology in this regard, this study offers a new perspective on migration research.

Recommendations:

The recommendations that emerge from the findings of this study offer new perspectives for managing the impacts of migration on societies and strengthening social integration:

Creative Social Integration Projects: Creative and innovative social integration projects that go beyond traditional integration approaches should be developed. These projects should allow migrants to preserve their culture and at the same time contribute to their new communities.

Economic Policies Responsive to Social Dynamics: Policies designed to promote economic integration should also take into account social dynamics. The economic success of migrants affects not only the well-being of individuals, but also that of society as a whole.

Multicultural Education Reforms: The education system should be reformed to better reflect the realities of multicultural societies. This should aim to equip students with the skills to understand and appreciate diverse cultures.

Comment:

The definition of Cyprus as an "island of migration" offers a new perspective for understanding the rich cultural diversity and social dynamics of the island. This identification allows us to see Cyprus not only as a site of migration, but also as a social laboratory based on the interaction of migrants and locals. In this context, Cyprus' identity as an island of migration can provide a new framework for future research and policy-making processes.

Contribution and Conclusion:

With the identification of Cyprus as an island of migration, this study suggests that an interdisciplinary approach should be adopted to better understand future migration flows and social integration. Bringing together cultural anthropologists, sociologists, geographers, and migration specialists to examine this unique identity of Cyprus in greater depth can contribute significantly to the future development of the island. Moreover, the identification of Cyprus as an island of migration can serve as a model for understanding and comparing migration phenomena in similar geographical regions.

In this context, it should be emphasized that these recommendations represent a crucial step forward in addressing migration not only as a problematic phenomenon but also as a dynamic that enriches societies. Future research should focus on the development of more effective strategies to strengthen social integration by examining the practical application of these recommendations.

RESTRICTION

The research is limited to the scientific sources that could be accessed and addressed during the literature review. As access to specific data or specific geographical areas was limited, it was not possible to take into account more specific studies conducted in these areas.

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